

Quantum Mechanics From Inertia Transforming Into Independent E and p Values? Part 3

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We have argued in Parts 1 and 2, that the free particle quantum form $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, which we call a complex probability, arises from special relativity in order to allow for conservation of energy and momentum (in an elastic collision). One may see from single particle bound states how $\exp(-iEt)$ plays the part of a binding energy.

We have noted in Parts 1 and 2, that $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ follows from the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$, but that one does not consider the deterministic $x=vt$ equation which applies to the center-of-mass, but rather treats t and x as independent variables which force the independence of E and p (two different interaction variables) and also force separate E and p conservation. The question becomes: How is it possible to have x,t play two such different roles in special relativity?

Here we try to answer this question. We argue that special relativity is based on determinism, i.e. $x=vt$. One may create a Lorentz transformation for a particle with rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ with t , a running variable. As seen from a frame moving with $-v$, one has $x'=vt'$. In other words, a separate x',t' is associated with each v . In Newtonian mechanics, it is possible to have mov_1 and mov_2 in the same frame (i.e. a frame with a ruler and clock), but in special relativity, each m_0 in the rest frame maps to a different x_1',t_1' and x_2',t_2' . This, however, seems to lead to a contradiction. If one considers two particles p_1,E_1 and p_2,E_2 (one dimensional motion) which elastically collide, then before the collision, they may be thought of as a composite particle (for more than a single x,t point) with energy E_1+E_2 and momentum p_1+p_2 . Given the validity of special relativity, we argue that one may associate a Lorentz invariant $-(E_1+E_2)t + (p_1+p_2)x$ with this composite particle. Furthermore, any outcome $E_i+E_j = E_1+E_2$ and $p_i+p_j = p_1+p_2$ would satisfy this same invariant. At this point there is no contradiction. The contradiction arises if one considers a single t and x for a composite particle, while internally there exist t_1',x_1' and t_2',x_2' . The composite particle, in terms of special relativity, is not compatible with each $-E't'+p'x$. The energies and momenta, however, add for each particle (in conservation equations) and so we argue that one should have a relativistically compatible approach which allows one to link each particle to a composite particle and see conservation of E and p .

We note that it is precisely $x=vt$ for each particle which leads to x_1',t_1' and x_2',t_2' and so argue that if one gives up this notion of determinism for x and t and introduces independent x, t values (fluctuations), then one can indeed retain the $-Et+px$ form for each particle and use it to create composite particles. This seems to give rise to an AND situation which does not exist for both p,x and E,t in the deterministic relativistic approach. In that approach, one can only think of p 's and E 's adding separately, without any linking of x 's and t 's. In the fluctuation approach, it is possible to have the same x and t fluctuation points for each particle. We argue that it is this kind of thinking which leads to the probabilistic form $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ which still respects the Lorentz invariant form and at the same time allows for conservation of E,p with the same t,x fluctuation points allowed. $x=vt$ does not allow one to combine x_1',t_1' and x_2',t_2' for a composite particle because these may coincide for only one x,t point and one wishes to describe a composite particle with an x,t which exists over more than one x,t . This is why we suggest the physical fluctuation scenario which exists together with $x=vt$. $x=vt$ describes the deterministic

motion of the center-of-mass, while $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ describes probabilistic hits in x and energy in t . It is special relativity which forces one to associate time fluctuations with E and spatial ones with p .

As a result, we argue that special relativity gives rise to both probabilistic and deterministic versions, both of which respect the form $-Et+px$. The deterministic version is linked with $x=vt$ center-of-mass motion, while $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ represents probabilistic appearances of E in t and p in x , i.e. there is a spatial probability for impulse hit delivery.

Deterministic Special Relativity

Deterministic special relativity may be developed using the deterministic $x=vt$ equation. This leads to m_0 at $x=0$ at t transforming to x',t' with

$$x'=vt' \quad \text{when seen from a frame moving with } -v \quad ((1))$$

If one has two m_0 particles at rest, then one transforms to x_1',t_1' under v_1 and the other to x_2',t_2' under v_2 . In other words, they are associated with very different x,t values. Momentum and energy values are given by:

$$E=mvcc/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad \text{and} \quad p=mv/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad (\text{one dimension}) \quad ((2))$$

Even though E and p are different for v_1,v_2 , conservation of energy (elastic collision) and momentum p , allow one to add these variables, but not x_1',t_1' and x_2',t_2' . One may only consider these two sets being the same at perhaps one collision point. The problem with this scenario is that as the particles become close (i.e. a range of x,t values) one may view them as a composite particle with:

$$\text{Energy} = E_1+E_2 \quad \text{momentum} = p_1+p_2 \quad (\text{one dimension}) \quad ((3))$$

$$\text{Any } E_i+E_j = E_1+E_2 \quad \text{and} \quad p_i+p_j = p_1+p_2 \quad \text{is also as good} \quad ((4))$$

If one respects special relativity, one should be able to write:

$$-(E_i+E_j) t + (p_i+p_j) x \quad ((5))$$

The problem is that E_i and E_j represent different particles with different x,t values and so a single t and x should not appear in ((5)), but do in order to have the Lorentz invariant. This suggests that t and x in ((5)) are not really associated with any $x=vt$ equation. Rather, they are some kind of variable which allows one to combine E and p values from each particle. If x and t are not deterministic variables in the $x=vt$ sense, and one wishes to have E and p independent for conservation reasons (see Part 2), then one must imagine a different kind of t and x . We suggest that the t and x to consider are fluctuation values which mean that there is an independence of E in t fluctuations and p in x fluctuations. This separation in x,t follows directly from special relativity because in the rest frame one only has fluctuations in time.

It is this approach which allows one to combine E,p,t,x expressions for two very different particles (different v values) at more than one x,t point and to establish a conservation of E and p separately through the introduction of a probability:

$$\exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((6))$$

The probabilistic nature appears when one assumes that x and t represent fluctuation points. In such a case, a particle with E1,p1 and E2,p2 may have partially overlapping fluctuation points. As a result, conservation of energy and momentum does not appear naturally in special relativity unless one introduces this notion of a fluctuating x and t. At the same time, one has $x=vt$ for the center-of-mass and must also have the deterministic special relativistic version. A fluctuation t or x value is a time or space point and so there is no reason why $-Et+px$ should apply to a composite particle. It is just that these x,t points cannot be directly linked to $x=vt$ as there is one $x=vt$ for each particle comprising the composite particle. This leads to the somewhat strange interpretation for the x and t values associated with the composite particle. If a fluctuation t,x exists for the composite particle (in a physical manner), then we argue that it should also exist for each constituent particle. This implies that a particle must have dual nature, namely an $x=vt$ center-of-mass behaviour and a probabilistic $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ x,t probabilistic fluctuation in terms of impulse hit location and energy in time appearance. As a result, special relativity seems to be more complicated than it first appears.

Conclusion

Special relativity is derived in a deterministic manner using the deterministic formula $x=vt$. This gives rise to deterministic formulas for $E=mv\gamma$ and $p =mv\gamma/c$. As a result, one might consider it highly unusual to try to introduce the notion of probability into such a deterministic theory. We argue, however, that one is led to a contradiction if one only considers $x=vt$. If one has two particles with the same m_0 at rest and views one from a frame moving with $-v_1$ and the other, $-v_2$, then x_1',t_1' and x_2',t_2' are different. One could have the particles coincide at one point (i.e. a single collision point x,t), but we argue that if one considers a composite particle for more than one x,t point, then one has a problem.

The composite particle (for conservation of E and p) has E_1+E_2 and p_1+p_2 (one dimension), but is actually equivalent to any $E_i+E_j=E_1+E_2$ and $p_i+p_j=p_1+p_2$. One should be able to write: $-(E_i+E_j) t + (p_i+p_j) x$, as argued in Part 2, but what do x,t represent? They don't seem to be linked with any $x=vt$, as one really has constituent particles. Each particle within the composite particle has a different x,t set. This is a paradox, it seems, unless one allows for x, t to be space and time points not linked with $x=vt$ motion.

In such a case, there should also be a second set of x,t for each constituent particle separate from $x=vt$. This allows one to combine constituent particles in such a manner that E and p are kept separate, i.e. are conserved separately. Physically, the way in which to achieve this is to consider x,t as probabilistic fluctuations, we argue, and so one must introduce, together with the deterministic $x=vt$, a probabilistic hit scenario in x,t, i.e. $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. In other words, special relativity is associated with a deterministic-probabilistic duality if one wishes to consider

composite particles at more than one x,t point. The notion of composite particles is important because they are linked with conservation of E and p .